

THE PROBLEM OF ORIGINALITY IN THE ANALYSIS OF PARALLEL CORPUS PRISM

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Abstract. This article talks about corpus linguistics, in particular parallel corpus, which is currently one of the most developed fields in world linguistics. The artistic text and its translated text in another language contain ideas about the difficulties that arise in the translation process. In particular, changes in the delivery of the original to readers of other languages in the source language and translation texts are covered in detail.

Key words. Corpus Linguistics, Parallel Corpus Texts (PKM) Source Language (MT), Translation Language (TT) parallel corpus of scientific texts, parallel corpus of mass media texts, parallel corpus of artistic texts.

In world linguistics, in the 60s of the 20th century, language corpora and their implementation in the language - the development of the interaction of corpus linguistics with computer technologies are clearly visible. The first example of corpus linguistics Brown's corpus, the first example of the 19th century, indicates that the theoretical foundations of this field date back to this period. Therefore, the automatic digitization of the intellectual wealth of mankind based on the electronic corpus has become an important part of modern linguistics. Due to this, corpus linguistics methods, types and the practice of corpus analysis are developing in various fields of linguistics in Uzbekistan.

The possibilities of information technologies in world linguistics have expanded and the connection of this field with linguistics has become stronger. That is, automatic translation, computer analysis, editing, thesaurus, electronic dictionaries related to linguistics have been created and they are being used in practice. The use of modern methods and tools in the teaching of language and literature, social sciences and foreign languages has been widely introduced. And while this demands the practical use of computers in these fields, the scientific theoretical study of corpus linguistics is gaining importance in all fields.

In computer linguistics, the term "corpus of texts" is widely used in the concept of "corpus". "Many of the world's languages have their own national corpora, which differ in the level of perfection, the ability to process text, today language corpora have become an undeniable working tool of modern linguistics for linguistic research and the solution of practical tasks, the corpus is more than a simple electronic library. difference, corpus annotation, concordance (relatively simple form of search engine) or corpus manager, its searchability, general requirements for corpus manager are explained. The linguistic significance of the corpus in the study of lexicography, lexicology, syntax, methodology, linguodidactics, mother tongue, and foreign language education is highlighted.

According to the criterion of parallelism, corpora are divided into monolingual, bilingual and multilingual. Contrast dialects and language variants in monolingual corpora. For example,

English as a mother tongue and English as a foreign language remained outside the scope of scholarly interest until the emergence of new technologies, which made it possible to attract much more speech works in the opposite language. Bilingual and multilingual corpora combine independently written texts in two or more languages in the same thematic field (for example, a collection of materials of conferences on a certain scientific problem held in different countries and in different languages). Such corpora help with terminology and are often used by translators. Another variant of a bilingual or multilingual corpus is the original texts written in any source language and the translation of these source texts into one or more other languages. Such a corpus will serve as an invaluable resource for comparative studies, research in translation theory, and the teaching of human and computer translation.

In the process of analysis of translations of works of art in the prism of parallel corpus, the study of the problem of originality in translated works takes an important place. It requires a great skill from the translator to translate a work written in one language into the translated language and deliver it to the readers of the whole world or other nations to convey the value and identity of this nation. In this case, the problem of originality, or in other words, the delivery of this people's life and way of life as much as possible, finds its expression in the parallel corpus.

Parallel corpus analysis has long been a crucial tool for linguistic and machine translation research. As researchers work to develop more accurate and comprehensive translation systems, they rely heavily on parallel corpora to train their models and improve translation quality. However, the problem of originality in the analysis of parallel corpus prism has become a growing concern in recent years.

The issue of originality arises from the fact that parallel corpora often contain translations of copyrighted texts. This means that researchers are not free to use the entire corpus for analysis without obtaining permission from the copyright holders. As a result, many researchers are limited in the scope of their analysis and may struggle to develop accurate models.

In addition, there is a lack of diversity in the datasets available for parallel corpus analysis. Many existing parallel corpora are created from publicly available sources such as news articles, legal documents, and government publications. This limited diversity can result in biased and incomplete language models that struggle to accurately capture the linguistic nuances of different genres and dialects.

Furthermore, the problem of originality in parallel corpus analysis presents a challenge for researchers who wish to develop innovative approaches to machine translation and language processing. Without access to a wide range of diverse and original texts, researchers may struggle to develop cutting-edge models that are capable of accurately capturing and translating the complexities of human language.

To address this issue, researchers and developers must work to create and maintain more diverse and original parallel corpora. This may involve obtaining permission to use copyrighted texts, collaborating with language experts to create new translations, and utilizing advanced techniques to anonymize and aggregate data from multiple sources.

In addition, it is crucial for researchers to continue advocating for policies and practices that support the development and use of original parallel corpora. This may involve working with government agencies and industry stakeholders to promote open access to language data and

ensure that researchers have the necessary resources to create and maintain diverse and original corpora.

Ultimately, the problem of originality in the analysis of parallel corpus prism presents a significant barrier to the development of accurate and effective translation models. However, by working to create more diverse and original datasets and advocating for open access to language data, researchers can continue to push the boundaries of machine translation and language processing.

In the parallel corpus, the data is actually compared with the original, and it is appropriate to present the problem of originality with several examples and arguments and type them into a logical chain. This allows you to control the changes in the procedures that occur during the translation process. The problem of originality is one of the important processes in the parallel corpus and helps to determine the quality of the translation, the skills of the translator, and whether the original text matches the average translation.

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